

fRamework for safE, opEn, collaboratiVe And inclUsive digitisAtion and management of cultural heritagE

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Full name
C & D	Communication & Dissemination
CCIs	Culture and Creativity Industries
CH	Cultural Heritage
DoA	Description of Action
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GLAMs	Galleries, Libraries, Museums and Archives
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SEP	Stakeholder Engagement Plan
WP	Work Package

Publishable summary

The Communication & Dissemination (C&D) Plan for the REEVALUATE project outlines the strategic approach the Communication and Dissemination Leader (HYP) is going to apply to effectively communicate and disseminate the project's objectives, progress, and outcomes. Our C&D plan is designed to ensure that the project's findings and innovative outcomes reach a wide audience, including cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), creative industries, academic researchers, policymakers, and the general public.

Our strategy includes identifying the target audience and utilizing digital platforms, such as the project website, social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook), newsletters, and webinars, traditional media, including press releases, articles in industry journals, and presentations at conferences and workshops.

The successful implementation of the C&D Plan will result in enhanced visibility and recognition of the REEVALUATE project, increased engagement and collaboration with key stakeholders, broad dissemination of project results leading to greater adoption and impact of the project's innovative outcomes, and a legacy of knowledge and best practices that can be utilized beyond the project's duration.

This C&D Plan will be a dynamic document that will be updated depending on the progress of the project and will be reported throughout the project in different deliverables, namely D5.5 – Communication and dissemination plan. R2(M18) and D5.6 – Communication and dissemination plan. R3(M36).

1 Introduction

REEVALUATE is a HORIZON EUROPE project, aimed to provide a holistic solution to the challenges of Cultural Heritage (CH) digitisation management, that will enable collaboration, creative reuse, and democratic and inclusive prioritisation and contextualisation of digitised cultural heritage artefacts. After assessing the current barriers and opportunities of CH digitisation, the project will develop a modular framework that will facilitate each stage of a digitised artefact's life cycle (prioritisation, contextualisation, storage, collaboration, and reuse) through a set of technological tools (enablers), free versions of which will be made available by the consortium for integration to the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH).

The REEVALUATE framework will be tested in 3 real-life pilot cases in 3 different European areas with varying CH and policy landscapes to ensure its applicability across Europe, demonstrating the framework's ability to manage the challenges associated with digitization of CH artefacts and their reuse within:

- 1) the Fashion and Gaming industries: reuse of digitized CH artefacts to create a Fashion-Themed Mobile Game and Personalized Garments
- 2) the Advertising industry: digitized CH artefacts for creative and sustainable advertising
- 3) the Tourism industry: the case of Aquileia

Communication and Dissemination (C&D) are two very important pillars of the REEVALUATE project, as they will ensure the impact of the project's results on the target audience and can maximize the project's outreach and sustainability through the relevant C&D activities.

WP5 and specifically Task 5.1 of the REEVALUATE project focuses on disseminating and communicating the project's outcomes to ensure broad awareness and impact within the European cultural heritage (CH) sector. This WP includes coordinating all dissemination and communication activities and promoting project outcomes to also ensure visibility and sustainability beyond the project's lifespan.

1.1 Purpose of the deliverable

Deliverable 5.1 at this first version stands as a preliminary plan of our C&D strategy for the project's lifecycle and beyond. It will unveil relevant activities carried out in the first 6 months of the REEVALUATE project and provide a plan for the next phases of the project. Updates of this deliverable will be reported in later versions of this document, namely D5.5-Communication and dissemination plan.R2 (M18) and D5.6-Communication and dissemination plan.R3 (M36).

1.2 Methodology

The Communication and Dissemination (C&D) strategy of the REEVALUATE project is a dynamic and all-encompassing framework that aims to effectively disseminate the project's outcomes and foster engagement within the European Cultural Heritage (CH) sector. This strategy has been centred around Task 5.1, which covers the whole project length and coordinates all dissemination and communication initiatives. Ensuring that all activities are strategically aligned to foster understanding of cultural heritage digitization, raise awareness of the project's objectives and outcomes, and support the exploitation and widespread use of the expected results requires the development of a detailed plan for dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) targets.

This deliverable captures contributions from all Consortium members as well as task-dedicated partners. Each partner has brought unique expertise and perspectives, enriching the overall strategy. Lastly, it is targeting public audiences and stakeholders involved in the cultural heritage (CH) sector.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

This document is divided into the following chapters and corresponding sections:

- Chapter 2 “C&D Strategy”: This section will uncover our C&D strategy, namely its objectives, identified target audiences and stakeholders, and key communication messages.
- Chapter 3 “External Communication”: In this section we’ll set the ground on the relevant communication tools used in the project, namely the language of the project, the project identity, acknowledgement and disclaimer of the project, website, social media channels, videos, e-Newsletters, and press releases.
- Chapter 4 “Dissemination”: This chapter summarizes all dissemination tools and activities foreseen, such as dissemination material, scientific publications, policy briefs, workshops, webinars, events, conferences, and clustering and networking activities.
- Chapter 5 “Pilot cases C&D strategy”: This chapter will cover the C&D strategy we are going to implement exclusively for the pilot cases and their corresponding target audiences.
- Chapter 6 “KPIs – C&D monitoring”: In this section we’ll present C&D relevant KPIs and monitoring tools to keep track of the C&D approach and its effectiveness.
- Chapter 7 “EC tools for C&D”: This chapter will offer insight on the free and available tools as offered by the EC to help disseminate and communicate our project to wider audiences.
- Chapter 8 “Internal Communication”: In this chapter we summarize the tools and practices we are going to use in order for all consortium partners to communicate with each other effectively.

A conclusion is summing up key points and next steps for the upcoming phases of the REEVALUATE project. Lastly, in the annexes, specific tools already used but will continue to be used are presented, namely C&D Monitoring tool, Scientific Journals Collector, and Conferences & Events Collector.

2 C&D Strategy

The C&D strategy we are going to implement within Work Package (WP) 5 for the REEVALUATE project follows a phase-oriented approach as described below:

- **Activation phase (M1-M6):** During this initial phase, the focus is on formulating an initial C&D plan and generating preliminary awareness within relevant sectors. The consortium has established by M3 a common project identity stimulating interest in the expected results through the creation and distribution of customized dissemination materials and the promotion of the project website. Additionally, an indicative schedule of communication activities has been prepared, which will include potential participation in scientific conferences, webinars, cultural and business fairs, as well as a list of potential public events, workshops, and training sessions for the next phases of the C&D plan’s execution. To ensure coordinated stakeholders’ engagement, a preliminary exploitation plan will also be developed and delivered by M6 (D5.4 REEVALUATE business models and exploitation plan. R1).
- **Execution phase (M7-M26):** This phase involves the implementation of the D&C plan, including the execution of planned communication activities, dissemination of project updates and results, and engagement with stakeholders through various channels.
- **Final phase (M27-M36 and beyond):** In the final phase and beyond, efforts will continue to disseminate project outcomes, evaluate the effectiveness of communication activities, and explore opportunities for sustaining the project's impact beyond its completion.

This deliverable stands as a basis in the **Activation phase** of the project to map and propose the relevant C&D activities for the next phases.

2.1 C&D objectives

WP5 is a work package relating horizontally to all other work packages of the project with the aim to diffuse the REEVALUATE outcomes and results. This deliverable outlines the plan, including the time and the manner for the REEVALUATE Consortium to ensure the project's visibility and maximization of impact in terms of research, market adoption, policies, and practical significance.

It is often difficult to distinguish the difference between C&D. However, the activities and work can be divided indeed as follows:

- **Communication activities:** Communication activities raise awareness and engage with the public about the project's activities and achievements, explaining the wider relevance of science and innovation to society. Communication can be done through various channels (press releases, articles, blogs, podcasts, videos, infographics, events, etc.).
- **Dissemination activities:** Dissemination activities include any action involving the public dissemination of project findings through any appropriate means, making results available to the people that can best make use of them, such as the scientific community, industry, policymakers, civil society, and more. Dissemination can be done through various channels, for example, through scientific publications, conferences, workshops, webinars, newsletters, social media and websites.

The objectives of the overall C&D strategy for REEVALUATE are (visualised briefly in Figure 1 as well):

- To disseminate REEVALUTE outcomes, including research findings, methodologies, tools, and technologies, to facilitate their use and future adoption by relevant stakeholders and communities.
- To increase awareness among stakeholders about the project's goals, objectives, and expected outcomes in the field of CH digitisation.
- To share progress, results, and best practices with CH professionals, CCIs, academia, policymakers, and the general public.
- To engage stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, gathering feedback, insights, and input to ensure that project activities and outputs are aligned with their needs and expectations.
- To foster collaboration and networking among stakeholders, encouraging partnerships, knowledge exchange, and joint initiatives in the field of CH digitization.
- To provide training, resources, and support to stakeholders to enhance their capacity and skills in digitisation, preservation, management, and reuse of CH assets.
- To inform policy development and decision-making processes at the local, national, and international levels by sharing evidence-based insights and recommendations derived from the project's research and activities.
- To contribute to the broader societal understanding and appreciation of CH, its preservation, and its significance for current and future generations.
- To increase the visibility and recognition of the project, its consortium partners, and stakeholders, both within the CH domain and among broader audiences interested in heritage preservation and digital innovation.
- To lay the groundwork for the long-term sustainability of project outcomes, ensuring that they continue to benefit stakeholders and contribute to the advancement of CH digitization beyond the project's duration.

Figure 1 C&D strategy objectives for REEVALUATE (taken from WP5 presentation for the 2nd plenary meeting)

2.2 Target Audience and Stakeholders

REEVALUATE will target specific groups and stakeholders as presented in the table below.

Table 1 C&D Target audiences

Target Audience	Description
CHIs	Museums, galleries, archives, libraries, and historic sites
CCIs	Curators, historians, artists, designers, filmmakers, musicians, writers, advertisers, game developers and publishers
Academic and research institutions	Universities and research centres of CH, History and Archaeology, Fine Arts, Fashion, Computer Science, and Information Technology
Policy makers	National, regional, and local levels
Professional associations/societies	International Council of Museums, International Federation of Library Associations, and Institutions
Industry	Publishers, film producers, game development companies, marketing agencies, fashion designers, fashion houses, textile manufacturers, and fashion retailers, travel agencies, tour operators and hotels
General public	Local communities and citizens

2.2.1 Stakeholder Analysis

Stakeholder analysis is foreseen to be conducted in close collaboration with WP1. Table 2 depicts the stakeholder groups initially identified within Task 5.1.

Table 2 Indicative Needs, Interests, and Influence of different stakeholder groups.

Stakeholder Groups	Interests	Influence	Needs
CHIs	Solutions that improve access to digitized materials, collaboration with other institutions and stakeholders, and enable creative reuse of CH artefacts.	Significant influence in the CH sector and can drive adoption of digitization technologies and best practices within their institutions and networks.	Efficient digitisation processes, innovative solutions for engaging with audiences and promoting CH.

CCIs	Tools and resources that facilitate access to digitized CH, enable collaboration with CHIs and other stakeholders, and support innovative uses of CH materials in their work	CCIs play a crucial role in promoting CH and shaping public perceptions through their creative outputs. They can influence trends in cultural production and consumption, driving demand for digitized CH materials and innovative applications.	Access to digitized CH materials for research, inspiration, and creative reuse in various artistic and commercial projects.
Academic and research institutions	Tools and platforms that facilitate access to digitized CH materials, support interdisciplinary collaboration, and enable innovative research and teaching practices.	Shape scholarly discourse and contribute to advancements in the field of CH. They can influence the development and adoption of digitization standards, best practices, and methodologies.	Access to digitized cultural heritage materials for teaching, research, and scholarly communication
Policy makers	Initiatives that align with CH policies and strategies at national, regional, and local levels, promote public engagement with CH, and support economic development and tourism.	Shape cultural heritage policies, allocate funding, and establish regulations that impact digitization initiatives and the CH sector.	Solutions that promote the preservation, accessibility, and promotion of CH while addressing legal and ethical considerations.
Professional associations /societies	Initiatives that support professional development, foster collaboration, and networking, and promote ethical standards and innovation.	Influence industry standards, guidelines, and practices through their publications, events, and advocacy efforts	Advance the interests of their members and promote best practices in their respective fields
Industry	Solutions that facilitate access to high-quality digitized CH materials, support licensing and rights management, and enable creative and innovative applications in their respective fields.	Influence demand for digitized CH materials and shape market trends through their products, services, and marketing campaigns.	Access to digitized CH materials for commercial purposes, such as content creation, marketing, product design, and tourism.
General public	Initiatives that promote awareness, appreciation, and understanding of CH, enable participation and interaction, and foster a sense of belonging and identity.	General public shapes public perceptions and attitudes towards CH and can influence public policy, funding decisions, and support for CH initiatives through advocacy, activism, and participation in cultural activities and events.	Engage with CH in meaningful and accessible ways, both online and offline.

Task 1.2 of WP1 focuses on the identification and engagement of stakeholders within REEVALUATE from various sectors including CH, CCIs, academia, NGOs, and civil societies. This task aims to build partnerships with stakeholders to understand their needs and concerns regarding the digitization and management of CH. To achieve this, Task 1.2 involves stakeholders' analysis and mapping to identify key actors from the

different stakeholder groups (Table 2) likely to be impacted by the project outcomes. These stakeholders will be, categorized into four different focus groups (indicatively Figure 2) based on their interest, knowledge base, and influence on project outcomes¹:

1. Key stakeholders
2. Influencers
3. Interested stakeholders.
4. Passive stakeholders

Moreover, tailored engagement strategies for each stakeholder category will be jointly developed among Task 1.2 and WP5 to ensure their involvement and support throughout the project, including also clear and concise messaging that communicates the value proposition of the REEVALUATE project and its outcomes, key benefits, features, and potential applications in a way that will resonate with the different types of the target audience². Consistent messaging across all communication channels will reinforce the project's brand and positioning.

Stakeholder analysis is intertwined with C&D strategy as it can help ensure that C&D activities are impactful, relevant, and targeted. It assists in creating messages that connect with stakeholders, choosing the best distribution channels, and cultivating a climate of trust and cooperation—all crucial for accomplishing REEVALUATE’s goals (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Power-Interest grid for stakeholder mapping and engagement (made with Canva).

2.2.2 Suggestions for Stakeholder Engagement Plan

A preliminary and suggestive Stakeholder Engagement Plan (SEP) can be outlined in the following superficial and indicative steps as a proposition:

¹ GA, p.79

² GA, p.85

- Stakeholder identification & categorisation
- Stakeholder analysis and mapping
- Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (e.g., most appropriate communication channels and platforms for reaching out to stakeholders (e.g., email, social media, webinars, workshops))
- Communications activities (newsletters, social media posts, and website updates to keep stakeholders informed about project progress and upcoming events, stakeholder meetings, workshops, and webinars to provide opportunities for direct engagement and discussion, multimedia formats (videos, infographics) to effectively convey project goals, activities, and outcomes to diverse stakeholder groups)
- Feedback mechanisms
- Monitoring and evaluation

As stated already, this SEP will be concluded and decided upon jointly with Task 1.2 and will be accordingly reported in D1.2-Opportunities, risks, gaps and problems of the digitisation of cultural heritage artefacts(M8).

2.3 Key messages

This section summarises context of communication messages for the different target audiences (see Table 3), already shared within the first 6 months of the project and to be shared horizontally throughout the project’s lifecycle.

Table 3 Key communication messages to target audiences.

Target Audience	Needs	Context of Communication Messages
CHIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Solutions for digitizing, preserving, and managing their collections. ❖ Tools for enhancing access to CH assets. Strategies for engaging with digital audiences and promoting CH. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REEVALUATE offers innovative solutions for digitizing and preserving CH collections. • Our framework can help improve access to the institution's assets and engage with audiences digitally.
CCIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Access to digitized CH resources for research, inspiration, and creative projects. ❖ Tools and platforms for collaborating on CH projects and sharing their work with wider audiences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to explore REEVALUATE resources for accessing and reusing digitized CH assets in your creative projects. • To discover how our framework facilitates collaboration and innovation across diverse cultural and creative sectors. • To join community of creators and innovators to unlock the potential of digital CH.
Academic and research institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Research opportunities and resources for studying and advancing CH digitization. ❖ Collaboration opportunities with other institutions and industry partners to drive interdisciplinary research and innovation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To show that REEVALUATE has valuable research opportunities and resources for advancing knowledge in CH digitization. • To invite into our interdisciplinary network of researchers and

		<p>practitioners to collaborate on cutting-edge projects and initiatives.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How our framework can support your research goals and contribute to the advancement of digital CH.
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Insights and evidence to inform CH policies and strategies. ❖ Tools and frameworks for promoting CH preservation, accessibility, and sustainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To show how REEVALUATE research and outcomes can inform and support CH policy development at all levels. • To discover the potential of our framework to promote CH preservation, accessibility, and sustainability locally and regionally. • To invite into engagement with the project to shape policies and strategies that ensure the long-term protection and promotion of cultural heritage assets.
Professional associations/ societies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Collaborative initiatives and resources to advance global CH preservation and access goals. ❖ Platforms to share best practices, standards, and guidelines for CH management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To explore opportunities to collaborate with our project to advance global CH preservation and access objectives. • To invite them to join our network of professionals and institutions working to promote best practices and standards in CH management. • To contribute their expertise and insights to our project's efforts to enhance the international exchange and preservation of CH.
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Access to diverse and high-quality cultural content for creative and commercial purposes. ❖ Opportunities to incorporate CH themes and assets into their products, services, and marketing campaigns. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To discover how digitized CH assets can enrich their creative projects, products, and marketing campaigns. • To explore partnership opportunities on incorporating cultural heritage themes and assets into their offerings. • To join our community of content creators, marketers, and businesses leveraging digital CH for innovation and inspiration.
General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Opportunities to engage with and learn about their local CH. ❖ Access to digital resources and experiences that celebrate and promote cultural diversity and identity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To show how REEVALUATE is making local CH more accessible and engaging. • To explore digital tools and experiences that celebrate and preserve their community's unique cultural identity and heritage. • To engage with REEVALUATE to contribute their stories, memories, and knowledge to the preservation and promotion of their local CH.

2.4 Pilot cases C&D strategy

To verify the REEVALUATE framework's applicability throughout Europe, **3 real-world pilot cases³** in 3 distinct European areas with 3 distinct CH and policy landscapes will be conducted in accordance with the WP4 activities. These 3 anticipated REEVALUATE pilots, which cover the 3 CCI sectors of **gaming, fashion, and advertising** in addition to the tourism sector, will help to implement the project's goals of validating the suggested framework and tools and disseminating a best practice guide to enable all stakeholders to successfully navigate towards the digital transition of CH.

The REEVALUATE pilot cases are:

- **Pilot 1 - Fashion Time Machine: Reusing Digitized CH Artefacts to Create a Fashion-Themed Mobile Game and Personalized Garments**
- **Pilot 2 - From Museums to Screens: Leveraging Digitized CH Artefacts for Creative and Sustainable Advertising**
- **Pilot 3 - From Public Sensing to Virtual Tours: The Case of Aquileia**

As described, REEVALUATE includes pilots in specific different EU Member States, which may influence our C&D strategy. In order to address this, culturally relevant communication will be ensured by customizing content to match the distinct cultural, linguistic, and societal circumstances of each pilot location. Through localized events, workshops, and presentations, the pilots can provide excellent chances to highlight the useful uses of the REEVALUATE framework.

The C&D strategy focused on each pilot case will align with the specific interests, preferences, and needs of the target audience while emphasizing the innovative and transformative potential of the REEVALUATE framework in diverse cultural and creative sectors. Additionally, the C&D strategy focused on the pilot cases will help us reach the corresponding KPIs (see Chapter 5).

Table 4 Communication strategy focused on the 3 pilot cases.

Pilot Case	Specific Target Audience	Communication strategy
Fashion Time Machine	Gamers, fashion enthusiasts, game developers, fashion designers, CH professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Utilization of social media platforms popular among gamers and fashion enthusiasts to generate buzz and excitement around the pilot (Instagram, YouTube etc). ❖ Engagement with gaming communities, fashion influencers, and relevant industry forums to promote awareness and participation. ❖ Showcasing behind-the-scenes development updates, gameplay teasers, and sneak peeks of personalized garment designs to captivate the audience's interest.
From Museums to Screens	Advertising professionals, marketers, creative agencies, cultural institutions, policymakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Potential partnerships with advertising industry associations, and creative agencies to disseminate case studies, success stories, and best practices derived from the pilot. ❖ Webinars, workshops, and forums to demonstrate the potential of leveraging

³ GA, p.123

		<p>digitized CH artifacts in advertising campaigns.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Showcase possible sustainability and ethical considerations of using CH in advertising to align with industry trends and priorities.
<p>From Public Sensing to Virtual Tours</p>	<p>Tourism industry stakeholders, local communities, historians, archaeologists, policymakers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Collaboration with tourism boards, travel agencies, and local cultural organizations to promote virtual tours and immersive experiences featuring digitized CH artifacts. ❖ Potential engagement with travel influencers, heritage bloggers, and online travel communities to showcase the richness and diversity of CH destinations. ❖ Emphasis on the educational and cultural value of virtual tours in preserving and promoting heritage sites, particularly considering travel restrictions and sustainability concerns.

3 External Communication

In this section, all necessary means of communication with external audiences, namely stakeholders outside of the Consortium are presented, establishing also the project’s identity.

3.1 Language

REEVALUATE project will be using British English for spelling consistency. For further information and guidance, we recommend consulting the European Commission’s (EC) English Style Guide for authors and translators [1].

3.2 Project identity

3.2.1 Logos

The official logo of the REEVALUATE project was selected by the Consortium by means of voting among three options crafted by HYP. Most partners voted for the following logo (Figure 3) and so the project gained its visual identity.

Figure 3 REEVALUATE Logo

The logo is vibrant and segmented into six colourful parts, each containing a distinct icon: a knight’s helmet, a painting, interconnected nodes, a classical column, a gaming controller, and a torchbearer. These

elements collectively symbolize various aspects of CH, including historical artefacts, art, technology, ancient architecture, interactive digital experiences, and cultural events resembling the project’s pilot cases.

The interconnected nodes resemble the role of technology in making CH accessible and preserving it. The combination of traditional symbols (like the classical column and knight’s helmet) with modern icons (like the gaming controller and painting) suggests a blend of preservation and contemporary engagement methods. The torchbearer signifies the inclusion of significant cultural events, adding a dynamic aspect to the project. We believe that the logo effectively encapsulates the project's mission to embrace diverse aspects of CH through advanced technology and innovative, engaging methods.

Other variations of the REEVALUATE logo are presented in the table below (Table 5).

Table 5 REEVALUATE Logo representations

All communication materials, namely, the templates, reports and all dissemination materials for all activities will carry the logo. These variations of the logo are intended to be utilized, contingent upon the format and space available per case. Every variant maintains consistency and harmonizes with the overall project identity.

3.2.2 Colours

The colours selected to represent the project’s visual identity are presented in the following image (Figure 4).

Figure 4 REEVALUATE identity colours.

3.2.3 Typography

The selected fonts for the project's identity to be used in C&D materials are:

- PF FUTURA NEU BOLD – Primary interface
- PF FUTURA NEU MEDIUM – Secondary interface

Headings / Titles

PF Futura Neu 64 Pixels

Subheadings / Subtitles

PF Futura Medium 24 Pixels

Paragraphs

PF Futura Medium 16 Pixels

Figure 5 Examples of sizing of PF FUTURA NEU font.

Additional fonts that can be used in other activities but are prompt to the project's identity are: **Jost**, **Aptos**, **Calibri** and **Times New Roman** with sizing as fit or specifically stated in EC relevant rules for reporting documents.

3.2.4 Templates

Having selected the visual identity of REEVALUATE project, templates for both Microsoft word and Microsoft PowerPoint have been created by HYP. These templates will be used by all Consortium members throughout the project's lifecycle and specifically for meetings, presentations, documentation, and reporting.

Both templates, and all relevant ones that may need to be created, were and will be created in alignment with all applicable rules and regulations of the EC and will acknowledge EU funding accordingly (see Chapter 3.3).

3.3 Acknowledgements and disclaimer

Following the guidelines of the project's Grant Agreement (GA), all material to be used as C&D material for the project must and will carry the EU emblem and disclaimer, including conferences, webinars, workshops, leaflets, roll-up banners, brochures, newsletters etc., in both physical and digital form.

All partners are invited to adopt the following suggested uses as fit and seen in Table 6.

Table 6 REEVALUATE Disclaimer

REEVALUATE Disclaimer

Funded by the
European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101132389

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3.4 Website

Already in M3, HYP delivered live the REEVALUATE website with the following domain:

<https://reevaluate.eu/>

Immediately after the website's launch, all partners were invited to check the website and give their feedback for possible changes. The website will be constantly updated and enriched by HYPERTECH as the project progresses. Additionally, HYPERTECH intends to keep active the project website, including its public deliverables' section for three years beyond the completion of the REEVALUATE project.

The website has the following sections:

- Home: General information and overview of the project.
- About
 - At a Glance: Brief description of the project
 - Vision: REEVALUATE approach presented
 - Objectives: Key objectives of the project
 - Partners: REEVALUATE Consortium presented
- Methodology
 - Concept & Approach: more details on the REEVALUATE approach.
 - Work packages: Brief description of each WP.
- Use Cases
 - Fashion Time Machine: Short description of the 1st pilot case of the project
 - From Museums to Screens: Short description of the 2nd pilot case of the project
 - Virtual Tourism: Short description of the 3rd pilot case of the project
- Resources
 - Publications
 - Best practices
 - Communication Materials
 - Deliverables
 - Webinars
- News & Events

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101132389

- News
- Project events
- Training events
- Contact

In the following figures below, a sneak peek of every section is presented.

Figure 6 REEVALUATE website – home sneak peek.

Figure 7 REEVALUATE website – At a glance section.

The life-cycle of digitised artefacts contains a number of phases; the most important are artefact selection, digitisation, storage, contextualisation, reuse.

Figure 8 REEVALUATE website – Vision section.

REEVALUATE Key Objectives

- ▶ Provide a framework for better management and use of the digitisation of cultural heritage.
- ▶ Support collaborative and democratic digitization by integrating data mining from social media, direct human engagement, and AI-driven analysis.
- ▶ Facilitate the accessible and creative reuse of the digital cultural assets through AI techniques.
- ▶ Organize cultural heritage data, ensuring effective management of Intellectual Property Rights in digitized assets' reuse leveraging NFT and DTL protocols.
- ▶ Validate the results in three real-world pilot cases that tackle actual needs and issues of the digitisation process.
- ▶ Develop business plans ensuring the uptake of project results and recommendations by the main stakeholders.

Figure 9 REEVALUATE website – Objectives section.

The digitization process for cultural artefacts involves several key phases, including artefact selection, digitization, storage, contextualization, and reuse.

The overall concept of REEVALUATE is to guide each step of the digital lifecycle of cultural artefacts. We will develop various enablers and tools, both technological and non-technological, to empower and automate the process where possible. These tools and enablers will be tailored to meet the real needs of stakeholders, ensuring their effectiveness and adoption. Our solution will be rooted in the principles of **co-design** and **co-creation**, maximizing societal value and promoting collaboration and creative reuse of digitized artefacts.

Figure 10 REEVALUATE website – Concept & approach section.

REEVALUATE Work Packages

- ▶ WP1 Review of the Current State of digitisation of Cultural Heritage in Europe
- ▶ WP2: Semantic Management Enablers
- ▶ WP3: Collaboration & IPR Management Enablers
- ▶ WP4: Piloting and Validation of the REEVALUATE Framework
- ▶ WP5: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
- ▶ WP6: Project Management

Figure 11 REEVALUATE website – Work packages section.

Figure 12 REEVALUATE website – Use Cases sneak peek.

Figure 13 REEVALUATE website – Communication Materials sneak peek.

Figure 14 REEVALUATE website – Deliverables sneak peek.

Follow REEVALUATE on social media

Figure 15 REEVALUATE website – Contact tab.

All information shared via the website and the social media discussed above will be handled in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2].

In particular, as far as the website is concerned, it is designed to host:

- All open access and public deliverables of all WPs. For the sensitive/private deliverables, a publishable executive summary is envisioned to be published.
- Training material & webinars developed throughout the project.
- Communication materials, including logos, leaflet, roll-up banner.
- Pictures and videos taken in all events.
- News articles, publications (scientific and non-scientific), and press releases
- Videos created for promotional reasons.

At its core, the REEVALUATE website will function as a centralised repository of information related to the project. Updates will be made in communication with the REEVALUATE Consortium. Table 7 summarizes an indicative timeframe for website updates.

Types of updates	Indicative Timeframe	Description
Content Updates	Monthly, when milestones are reached, or when public content needs to be uploaded	Simple updates like adding new text, images, or news articles.
Structural Updates	Monthly – every 3 months	Adding new sections or pages, which might involve new design elements, creating new menus, integrating functionalities, and ensuring alignment with existing structure
Design Updates	If needed/demanded	Significant design changes, such as new layouts or graphic designs. This includes designing new elements, getting approvals, and implementing the changes.

Table 7 Indicative Timeframe for website updates

Through the project’s website, stakeholders, collaborators, and the general public can access comprehensive details about the project's objectives, activities, and outcomes. Based on professional design and filled with updated content, the website serves as a powerful tool to attract attention from relevant stakeholders, including potential collaborators, funders, and participants.

In addition, the website will serve as a platform for sharing project-related resources, including research findings, publications, reports, and multimedia content. Hosting these resources in a centralized location, the website will ensure easy access for stakeholders seeking valuable information to support their own work or interests in the field of CH. This resource-sharing capability enhances the project's impact and contributes to knowledge dissemination within the broader community.

There is also a dedicated section for newsletter subscriptions, where the users can sign up by inserting their email (Figure 16). The “unsubscribe” option will automatically exist in every group email the users will receive.

Figure 16 Dedicated section to subscriptions for REEVALUATE newsletters.

Finally, there is clear and direct link to the project’s social media profiles as well (Figures 15 & 17) to help the audience reach the project’s social media profiles easily.

Follow REEVALUATE on social media

Figure 17 Social media hyperlinks on REEVALUATE website.

3.5 Social Media Channels

The REEVALUATE project has the following available social media accounts, already created by M2-M3:

- LinkedIn: www.linkedin.com/company/reevaluate-project (Figure 18)
- X (twitter): twitter.com/ReevaluatePro (Figure 19)
- Instagram: www.instagram.com/reevaluatteeu/ (Figure 20)
- YouTube: www.youtube.com/@REEVALUATEproject (Figure 21)

Figure 18 REEVALUATE LinkedIn page (status up to 27.06.2024)

The image shows a screenshot of the REEVALUATE EU Project Twitter profile. The profile header includes the name "REEVALUATE EU Project", a back arrow, and "51 posts". The profile picture is the REEVALUATE logo, and there is an "Edit profile" button. The bio states: "The REEVALUATE project is dedicated to transforming the way cultural heritage institutions approach digitisation, embracing more open and inclusive pathways." Below the bio are links for "Community", "reevaluate.eu", and "Joined January 2024". It also shows "83 Following" and "52 Followers". The navigation tabs are "Posts", "Replies", "Highlights", "Articles", "Media", and "Likes". The first tweet is from 20 hours ago, announcing "WP6: Project Management" led by @CERTHellas, with a "Promote" button and a menu icon. The tweet text describes the focus of WP6. Below the text is a graphic with the REEVALUATE logo, the text "WORK PACKAGE" in two overlapping boxes, and a yellow circle with the number "6".

Figure 19 REEVALUATE X(twitter) account (status up to 27.06.2024)

Figure 20 REEVALUATE Instagram account (status up to 27.06.2024)

Figure 21 REEVALUATE YouTube channel (status up to 27.06.2024)

In the first 6 months of the project there has already been content created and shared in all social media accounts. Posts involved introductions of consortium partners, introduction of WPs and related description of work, promotion of the project’s website and newsletter subscriptions, dedicated posts on relevant

international days to promote the project’s vision and objectives, and lastly all relevant posts to accommodate T1.2 needs. To attract more stakeholders and to also increase visibility of the project, relevant social media groups have been identified with focus on CH in Europe and internationally.

Regarding the thematic of social media posting and blogging, Indicative categories in all channels involve:

- REEVALUATE (objectives, scope, outcomes) & Consortium.
- Technologies
- Pilot cases
- CH industry news
- Innovations
- News, project events, participation in external events
- Webinars/workshops
- Multimedia
- Business models
- CH policies

Relevant hashtags that have been already established and used are: **#REEVALUATEproject**, **#HorizonEurope**, **#CulturalHeritage**, **#DigitisationManagement**.

Suggested hashtags that partners can use are presented (but are not limited to) in the table below:

Table 8 Hashtags and subjects for social media engagement

Thematic	Relevant Hashtags
Project-specific	#REEVALUATE, #CulturalHeritage, #Digitisation, #CHManagement, #Innovation, #HorizonEurope, #Collaboration
Content-specific	#CreativeReuse, #CHI, #Archives, #DigitalPreservation, #CreativeReuse, #CommunityEngagement #CrossFertilization
Trending/seasonal	#TechTuesday (example of establishing one weekday to promote technical information of the project), #WorkPackageWednesday (example of establishing one weekday to promote WP-related content) #ResearchHighlight

In addition to Table 8, we have identified specific annual dates, relevant to the project and its scope, which can be exploited in order to disseminate news, updates, and outcomes of the REEVALUATE project as it progresses (see Table 9).

Table 9 Date Relevant content for C&D.

Date	Objective
World Heritage Day (April 18)	To raise awareness about the diversity of cultural heritage and the efforts required to protect and conserve it
International Museum Day (May 18)	To showcase advancements in museum practices, including digitization, and promote public engagement with digital collections, also promoting news relevant to the pilot cases
International Archives Day (June 9)	To emphasize the role of digitization in preserving historical documents and archives
European Heritage Days (September)	To promote interest in CH and encourage public engagement with CH

World Tourism Day (September 27)	To highlight the role of tourism in promoting cultural heritage and fostering economic development
World Audio-Visual Heritage Day (October 27)	To raise awareness about the importance of preserving audiovisual documents through digitization
World Digital Preservation Day (First Thursday of November)	To promote the importance of preserving digital content and ensuring its long-term accessibility.

It is of great importance that all partners of REEVALUATE actively contribute to published content. A suggested timeline and schedule for partners to be assigned as “Content Creators” will be shared after M7, to effectively engage all consortium members.

Additionally, an excel sheet will be shared with the rest of the REEVALUATE Consortium (see Annex I) to monitor and keep track of everyone’s C&D activities. This online excel will be hosted under the project’s common online repository in Next Cloud, hosted by CERTH.

3.6 Videos

In the REEVALUATE website and corresponding YouTube channel, a first introductory video has been already created to initially promote the project and its vision. Such content and short videos are envisioned to be created to increase the visibility of the project. FFP will also specifically undertake the creation of a promo video for the second pilot case reusing digitised CH objects⁴.

This content will be used on all communication channels of our C&D strategy. Recordings of webinars and workshops will also be uploaded and made available online.

3.7 e-Newsletters

e-Newsletters will ensure C&D at European and International levels and keep stakeholders informed and updated on the project’s findings, status, developments, events, and publications.

At least 2 e-newsletters per year are foreseen already, with the number of total 9 e-newsletters produced throughout the project. The first newsletter is planned to be created and sent in M6. An indicative planning of e-newsletter publications can be seen in Table 10 below.

Table 10 Indicative schedule of newsletters throughout the project

Newsletters Initial Schedule	
<i>1st newsletter</i>	M6
<i>2nd newsletter</i>	M12
<i>3rd newsletter</i>	M15
<i>4th newsletter</i>	M18
<i>5th newsletter</i>	M22
<i>6th newsletter</i>	M26
<i>7th newsletter</i>	M30
<i>8th newsletter</i>	M32
<i>9th newsletter</i>	M36

3.8 Press Releases

Press releases will play a significant role in the dissemination of critical updates, successes, and discoveries within the REEVALUATE project. In the first 6 months of REEVALUATE, there have not been any press

⁴ GA, p.125

releases created yet, however the communication leader (HYP) envisages the first one to be released in the first year of the project, early in the **Execution Phase**. They will highlight the goals of the project, the consortium members, and the expected results at various phases of the project's lifespan. Press releases will also be useful for announcing critical milestones, such the completion of the different project phases, the deployment of successful pilot projects, or the sharing of research results. They will therefore provide a brief synopsis of each accomplishment along with its implications for the project's future development and wider effects on related communities and stakeholders.

Throughout the project, at least 6 press releases are planned, targeting major stakeholders, to raise interest and possibly recruit. In addition to them, at least 2 press clippings are foreseen targeting the public to raise interest and awareness among non-specialists.

4 Dissemination

4.1 Dissemination Material

Already by M3 a leaflet and a roll-up banner were created to be used as dissemination materials. The leaflet is presented as a compact booklet and is already available in English language in two versions: printable and digital. It includes key information about the project like REEVALUATE approach, impact, objectives, Consortium, and links to the project's website and social media channels.

The roll-up banner is available also in English and digital and printable forms. It includes brief information on the project's scope, values, objectives, approach, use cases and impact, along with a timeline of key milestones, and Consortium.

Dissemination materials are envisioned to be updated further in **Execution** and **Final Phases** of the project. Consortium partners will give their feedback on relevant material, digital or printed, specifically on the content that they are or could be responsible for.

Such materials will be used for dissemination and promotion purposes at conferences, potential fairs, meetings, seminars, or workshops.

4.2 Scientific publications

As stated in the GA, all results and research outputs will be aligned with the Open Access and Open Science regulations of EU. Project publications will be published in Open Access Journals checked in **SHERPA/RoMEO platform** and **DOAJ**, and Open Access Repositories namely **PubMed**, **Zenodo**, **arXiv**, identified through ROAR, OpenDOAR, OpenAIRE and OAD. Additionally, the involved researchers will utilize both Green Open Access and Gold Open Access.

- More than 25 scientific publications are foreseen throughout the project. To name (but not to be limited to) a few examples of relevant journals: Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage
- Cultural Heritage and Science
- Journal of Cultural Heritage
- Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development
- Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage

A corresponding repository has been created to help gather information from partners, keep track of all available journals and of the corresponding actions from relevant partners (see Annex II). The responsible partners will provide a planning of relevant publications.

4.3 Policy briefs

Policy briefs can serve as concise, informative documents aimed at policymakers, governmental agencies, and other relevant stakeholders, elucidating key issues, challenges, and opportunities pertaining to CH digitization and management. Such documents can synthesize research findings, best practices, and policy recommendations derived from the project's activities, offering actionable insights for informed decision-making.

In REEVALUATE it is aimed to generate policy briefs and best practices guidelines for CCIs from the demonstrators' analysis, as foreseen in Task 5.3 that will be specifically reported in D5.3-REEVALUATE policy scenarios and evidence-based recommendations (M36).

4.4 Workshops, webinars, events, and conferences

Workshops are envisaged in WP1 to extract valuable information from relevant stakeholders, as well as in WP5 in the context of engaging with target audiences or even creating synergies with other projects, not to be further discussed in this deliverable. Especially through co-design workshops and training events, it will be feasible to collaborate with multiple stakeholders to design exhibitions, interpretive materials, and digital platforms for accessing CH resources. Throughout the project's lifecycle 2 Open Day workshops (M24, M36) and more than 10 technical workshops are foreseen, as well as the creation of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs).

For CHIs to become more digitally adept and capable of capitalising on the opportunities of digital CH, training webinars are envisioned to be developed and specifically a minimum amount of 12.

For dissemination of the project participation in more than 15 scientific conferences is also foreseen, along with more than 9 symposiums or fairs.

We aim to constantly search for annual and periodical conferences and events taking place throughout Europe, utilizing web search tools as in [3], [4], [5], or through the ones in [6], [7], [8], [9], [10].

To log and keep track of such existing events, a dedicated table has been developed, available online in the project's common directory for all Consortium partners to fill (see Annex III).

During the project, projects (sister projects and other relevant ones), as well as associations and networks related to CH will be mapped and approached to exchange best practice experiences, discuss barriers, policies, and regulations, and possibly established synergies. An initial identification has already taken place. All relevant activities related to synergies with other European projects and initiatives are part of Task 5.2 activities and will be exclusively reported in deliverables D5.2-Ecosystem development and building synergies report. R1 (M12) and D5.7-Ecosystem development and building synergies report. R2 (M30).

5 KPIs – C&D monitoring

In the following tables we present in total the distinct Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined to monitor and assess quantitatively and qualitatively the effectiveness of our C&D activities along with their consequent impact.

Table 11 Communication KPIs

Communication KPIs	Description
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In-house e-newsletters	9 e-newsletters
Promotional material, including video content	At least 12
Press releases targeting major stakeholders	At least 6
Press releases targeting general public.	≥ 2 press clippings

Table 12 Dissemination KPIs

Dissemination KPIs	Description
Organization of Workshops & Attendance to conferences	15 Conferences - 2 Open Day Workshops (M24, M36) 500 visitors - 10 speakers
Training events and the creation of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)	Training Events (M24, M36) - Set up of MOOC. 2 events - 1 MOO Course
On-site demonstrations and presentations	10 demonstrations - 10 presentations > 20 responders - 10 on-site demos
Open Access publications	Publication to journals & magazines > 25 publications
Online publishing (website, online magazines, blogs, etc.)	> 15 publications and 4 blog post per month > 200 views / Public. / Year
Customizable marketing packages (videos, how-to demos, press kit etc)	Production of professional material tailored to specific audiences. > 5 products > 20 distributions

Table 13 Pilot cases related C&D KPIs

Pilot Cases	C&D KPIs
Pilot 1 - Fashion Time Machine: Reusing Digitized CH Artefacts to Create a Fashion-Themed Mobile Game and Personalized Garments	Number of participants engaged in the collaborative contextualisation and prioritization process.
	Number of users of the mobile game developed by NURO
	Feedback and satisfaction surveys from participants and stakeholders involved in the pilot. Number of media mentions and press coverage of the pilot.
Pilot 2 - From Museums to Screens: Leveraging Digitized CH Artefacts for Creative and Sustainable Advertising	Number of participants engaged in the collaborative contextualisation and prioritization process
	Feedback and satisfaction surveys from participants and stakeholders involved in the pilot. Number of media mentions and press coverage of the pilot
Pilot 3 - From Public Sensing to Virtual Tours: The Case of Aquileia	Number of participants engaged in the collaborative contextualisation and prioritization process
	Feedback and satisfaction surveys from participants and stakeholders involved in the pilot.

	Number of media mentions and press coverage of the pilot.
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5.1 Preliminary roadmap of activities

In the following table (Table 14) we propose an indicative and preliminary action plan of C&D activities that will allegedly help us reach the proposed KPIs. This indicative roadmap may cover the whole duration of the project and has been drafted to be annual. This roadmap may undergo changes and adaptations according to the project's needs as it evolves.

Table 14 Preliminary roadmap of C&D activities

Phase	Description	C&D activities	Planned actions
Activation Phase (M1-M6)	Initial Planning and Setup	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brand identity design ▪ Communication kit development ▪ Project website creation ▪ Social media channels set up ▪ E-Newsletter publication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Website launch by M3 ▪ Communication material ready by M3 ▪ 1 e-newsletter ▪ 1 blog post
Execution Phase (M7-M26)	Establishing presence and engagement, expanding outreach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Communication kit updates ▪ Project website updates ▪ In-house e-newsletters ▪ Promotional Material, including Video Content ▪ Press releases for major stakeholders ▪ Press releases for general public ▪ Workshops & conferences ▪ Training events & MOOCs ▪ On-site demonstrations ▪ Open Access publications ▪ Blog posts & online publishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Updates in leaflets, roll-ups banners, presentations per case ▪ Website constantly updated ▪ 6 newsletters by M26 (according to schedule) ▪ At least 6 promotional materials/videos by M26 ▪ At least 3 press releases for major stakeholders by M26 ▪ At least 1 press release for general public by M18 ▪ 8 conferences, 1 Open Day Workshop at M24 ▪ 1 training event at M24, 1 MOOC by M26 ▪ 5 demonstrations on-site by M26 ▪ Approx. 12 publications by M26 ▪ 4 blog posts per month
Final Phase (M27-M36 and beyond)	Intensifying engagement, final pushes for sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Communication kit updates ▪ Project website updates ▪ In-house e-newsletters ▪ Promotional Material, including Video Content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Updates in leaflets, roll-ups banners, presentations per case ▪ Website constantly updated. To be active

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Press releases for major stakeholders ▪ Press releases for general public ▪ Workshops & conferences ▪ Training events & MOOCs ▪ On-site demonstrations ▪ Open Access publications ▪ Blog posts & online publishing 	<p>for 2 years after project completion.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 3 e-newsletters by M36 ▪ At least 6 promotional materials/videos by M36. ▪ At least 3 press releases for major stakeholders by M36 ▪ At least 1 press release for general public by M30, 1 final press release after M36 ▪ 1 training event at M36, MOOC update by M36 ▪ 5 demonstrations, 5 presentations by M36 ▪ Approx.13 publications by M36 ▪ 4 blog posts per month
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6 EC tools for C&D

It is widely known that EC offers various free-of-charge services to support the C&D of the European projects. We aim to make use of the available following ones, as fit per project phase and scope of outcomes:

- Open research Europe platform [11]
- Horizon Dashboard [12]
- Horizon Results platform [13]
- Innovation Radar [14]

With regards to the Horizon Results Booster, given the fact that it terminates on June 2024[15], we aim to monitor and examine other possible free tools that the EC may offer as an alternative.

7 Internal Communication

Internal communication refers to the communication among REEVALUATE Consortium members. This communication is the core of smooth, effective, and efficient execution of the project. Effective internal communication, idea exchange, and collaboration across work packages are therefore crucial.

The following communication tools (Table 15) are being and will be used by Consortium members for daily and periodic communication.

Table 15 Tools for internal communication.

Communication Tool	Description
Emails	These can be used for formal and official communication. The REEVALUATE mailing list will remain always open for new partner contacts to be added, when necessary, and for any related modifications in general.
Microsoft Teams	Online meetings in groups or 1-on-1

GoToMeet	Online meetings in groups or 1-on-1
Nextcloud repository	CERTH as the coordinator of the project has created and shared with all partners a nextcloud online repository for the project. This online folder is being used as a common directory also for all relevant C&D materials, activities, reporting, and monitoring as well.

Ensuring all partners are on board using the established tools, having regular check-ins and status updates meetings (project plenary meetings, WP-specific online meetings, and task-specific online meetings) sharing best practices, encouraging regular feedback from all partners, we can ensure an effective and seamless communication among Consortium partners throughout the project.

8 Conclusion

The C&D Plan is an essential element of the REEVALUATE project and it will be updated throughout the project’s lifecycle. It is meant to guarantee efficiency in communicating the objectives and findings, reaching far and wide. We aim to engage our stakeholders, promote our innovations, and ensure the long-term impact of our work through our structured and strategic approach, as presented in this initial version of planning in the **Activation Phase**.

In the **Execution** and **Final Phases** of the project, we will focus on building momentum, regularly sharing progress through newsletters, promotional materials, and press releases, actively participating in conferences, workshops, and training events to foster knowledge exchange and collaboration. Our goal is to establish a strong foundation and maintain consistent communication with all audiences.

The present C&D strategy developed for the REEVALUATE project satisfactorily fulfils the challenges and heterogeneity of demands linked with CH digitisation across Europe. The purposeful employment of various means of communication, including consistent project identity, active presence on social media, and producing professional and qualitative materials, demonstrates the significance and impact of C&D planning. Having clear KPIs and a preliminary outline of activities offers a solid structure of how to monitor and assess our C&D activities, so the Consortium can stay on track towards the project’s goals. The inclusion of EC tools for C&D and the internal communication plan enhances the cohesiveness and efficiency of all partners’ endeavours.

In conclusion, this deliverable is not just a static plan but a dynamic one, which promotes the long-term sustainability and broader societal appreciation of CH. D5.1 sets the basis for a concrete C&D strategy that will be horizontally applied and updated throughout the project, while reporting of its outcomes will be presented all phases of the project.

References

English Style Guide. A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission. (14 November 2023). Brussels: European Union.

[11] <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu>

[12] <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

Annex II Scientific Journals Collector

In Annex II the scientific journals information collector is presented, which is an online excel table for all partners to store basic information about the scientific journals they are going to/are planning to publish in. This online excel will be available in the common online repository for REEVALUATE in Next Cloud, hosted by CERTH.

Journal	USD	EUR	Green Access (indicate using [X])	Golden Access (indicate using [X])	Embargo (time)	License

Annex II Figure 1 Scientific Journals information collector

Annex III Conferences & Events Collector

In Annex III the Conferences & Events information collector is presented, which is an online excel file to gather basic information about Conferences (Annex III Figure 1), Events/Fairs (Annex III Figure 2), and Networking opportunities (Annex III Figure 3). This online excel will be available in the common online repository for REEVALUATE in Next Cloud, hosted by CERTH.

Conference	Place	Time	Partners (drop down list)	Paper deadline	Application deadline	Notes	Website
CIDOC 2024	Amsterdam	11-15 November 2024		10 May 2024	28 October 2024	Early bird tickets: € 385 (members ICOM: €325) Regular tickets: € 425 (members ICOM: € 365) Student tickets: € 125 Livestream tickets: € 75 Early bird tickets are available till 30 July or earlier if sold out.	https://www.njksmuseum.nl/en/whats-on/lectures-symposiums/cidoc2024
21 st EuroXR International Conference	Athens	27-29 November 2024		with rebuttal procedure: May 6, 2024 without rebuttal procedure: June 24, 2024	End August 2024 (early)	fees applied: https://www.euroxr.org/conference-2024/registration	https://www.euroxr.org/conference-2024
Herbsttagung der Fachgruppe Dokumentation des Deutschen Museumsbundes	Berlin	14.-16.10.2024	SPK			no fees. This meeting takes place every	https://www.museumbund.de/termine/herbsttagung-2024-der-fachgruppe-dokumentation/

Annex III Figure 1 Conferences & Events information collector: "Conference" tab

Event/Fair	Place	Time	REEVALUATE participation	Partners (drop down list)	Application deadline	Notes	Website

Annex III Figure 2 Conferences & Events information collector: "Events & Fairs" tab

Networking Opportunity	Place (if applicable)	Time (if applicable)	Partners	Paper deadline (if applicable)	Application deadline (if applicable)	Notes	Website
Digital Library - Central Institute for the Digitalization of the Cultural Heritage (Italian Ministry of Culture)		-	AQUILEIA	-	always submittable	Sharing ideas, aspirations, projects and results is the first step to creating a stable network between individuals and institutions oriented towards the pursuit of common objectives. The Institute wants to form communities around emerging themes. This is why the Digital Library asks its users to report ideas, projects and good practices using the form below. Proposals in line with the Institute's research aims will be included in the pages of the ACTIVITIES section of the site	https://digitallibrary.cultura.gov.it/partecipa/

Annex III Figure 3 Conferences & Events information collector: "Networking Opportunity" tab